

Terpenoids and Related Compounds. Part V¹. Triterpenoids from the Flowers of *Eugenia Jambolana* Lam.

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Two triterpene acids, oleanolic acid and crategolic acid (maslinic acid), have been isolated from the flowers of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam. as their respective methyl ester.

In a previous communication¹, we reported the isolation of betulinic acid, friedelin, *epi*-friedelinol, β -sitosterol, and eugenin[†], a new ester of *epi*-friedelinol from the stem-bark of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam. Nair and Subramanian² reported isolation from the flowers of *E. jambolana* of two new triterpenoids, 'Eugenia terpenoid A' and 'Eugenia terpenoid B' besides acetyloleanolic acid. In view of this and the reported³ medicinal uses of the different parts of the plant in the indigenous system of medicine, we thought it relevant to undertake a chemical investigation of the flowers.

By following a different extraction procedure, using benzene instead of ethanol², we obtained a crude semicrystalline product from the flowers of *E. jambolana*. The product was separated into ether-soluble and ether-insoluble fractions. The former fraction on extraction by cold aqueous alkali, followed by acidification of the alkaline extract, afforded a crystalline mixture of triterpene carboxylic acids, which was esterified with diazomethane, and the mixture of the methyl esters was chromatographed on deactivated alumina. The first ester, eluted from the column, on acetylation and crystallisation from acetone furnished methyl oleanolate acetate, m.p. 218-20°, [α]_D+65° (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen. Further, the acetate ester was hydrolysed to yield methyl oleanolate, m.p. 194-96°, [α]_D+70° (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen.

The second methyl ester, m.p. 227-28°, [α]_D+36° (CHCl₃), eluted from the column in the above chromatogram, had the molecular formula C₃₈H₅₀O₄ and was found to be identical (IR) with methyl crategolate (methyl maslinic)⁴. The structure of crategolic (maslinic)

1. This *Journal*, 1965, 42, 255.

2. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 457.

3. Chopra, Nayar, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 238.

4. (a) Tschesche and Fugmann, *Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 810.

(b) Tschesche *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 86, 626.

(c) Arthur and Hui, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1403.

(d) Tschesche and Poppel, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 320.

(e) Caglioti and Cainelli, *Atti Accad. Nazl. Lincei, Rend., Classe Sci., Fis. e. Mat.*, 1960, 29, 544; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 56, 7369f.

[†]Its mol. formula is C₃₈H₁₀₆O₂, but it was wrongly printed as C₃₈H₁₀₆O₂₉ in Part IV.

acid has recently been established⁵⁻⁶ as 2 α , 3 β -dihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (I: R=Me; R₁=R₂=H). Further, our methyl crategolate (I: R=Me; R₁=R₂=H) was converted into methyl crategolate diacetate (I: R=Me; R₁=R₂=COMe) which was found to be identical (IR) with an authentic specimen.

The above mentioned ether-insoluble part was separated into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble fractions. Each of the fractions was esterified with diazomethane and chromatographed when only methyl oleanolate and methyl crategolate could be isolated from each. We, however, failed to isolate any acetyloleanolic acid⁷ and Eugenia terpenoids A and B² from the flowers of *E. jambolana*.

* EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction of the Flowers of E. Jambolana.—The dried flowers (1 kg.), collected during the summer of 1964, were extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus for 8 hr. The crude, semicrystalline solid (60 g.), left after removal of benzene, was digested with ether; the ether-soluble material was separated by filtration from the ether-insoluble matter (18g.). The ether solution was extracted with cold aqueous 5% NaOH solution and the alkaline aqueous layer acidified with cold HCl (dil.) and filtered when a crystalline acidic material (22 g.) was obtained.

Crude Methyl Oleanolate.—The above ether-soluble acidic matter (22 g.) in ether (1 litre) was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (prepared from 20 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and allowed to stand overnight. After working up as usual, the ester mixture (16 g.) was chromatographed over alumina (300 g., deactivated with 9 ml of 10% acetic acid). Elution with benzene afforded the crude solvated methyl oleanolate (5 g.), m.p. 110-14°.

Methyl Oleanolate Acetate.—The above crude methyl oleanolate (1.5 g.) was acetylated with acetic anhydride (15 ml) and pyridine (15 ml) in the usual manner. The crude acetate on crystallisation from acetone afforded methyl oleanolate acetate (0.4 g.), m.p. 218-20°, [α]_D+65° (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 77.50; H, 10.30. Calc. for C₃₃H₅₂O₄: C, 77.29; H, 10.22%).

*All melting points are uncorrected. The petroleum used had b.p. 80-80°.

5. (a) Caglioti *et al.*, *Gazzetta*, 1962, **92**, 309.

(b) Caglioti and Cainelli, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1061.

6. Tschische *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1934, **572**, 175.

Methyl Oleanolate from Methyl Oleanolate Acetate.—Methyl oleanolate acetate (0.22 g.) was deacetylated by refluxing in benzene (2 ml) with a solution of methanolic NaOH, prepared from NaOH (0.5 g.), water (0.5 ml), and methanol (4.5 ml). After working up as usual, the crude hydroxy-ester (0.2 g.) on crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and methanol furnished methyl oleanolate, m.p. 194-96°, $[\alpha]_D^{+70}$ (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 79.59; H, 10.68. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₃: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%).

Methyl Cratogolate (Maslinate).—Elution with ether in the above chromatogram furnished a crude solid (2 g.), m.p. 212-16°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum yielded methyl cratogolate (0.65 g.), m.p. 227-28°, $[\alpha]_D^{+36}$ (CHCl₃), identical (IR) with an authentic sample of methyl cratogolate. It developed a yellow colour with tetranitromethane. (Found: C, 76.24; H, 10.23; M.W. (Rast), 473. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₄: C, 76.50; H, 10.36%; M.W., 486).

Methyl Cratogolate Diacetate.—The acetate of methyl cratogolate was prepared by treating methyl cratogolate (0.52 g.) with pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) at the room temperature for 4 days. The crude glassy mass (0.5 g.), obtained after working up as usual, was chromatographed over alumina (50 g., deactivated with 1.5 ml of 10% acetic acid). Elution with benzene provided the crude acetate, m.p. 138-58°, which on crystallisation from dilute methanol furnished pure methyl cratogolate diacetate⁴ (0.11 g.), m.p. 166-68°, $[\alpha]_D^{+24}$ (CHCl₃), identical (IR) with an authentic specimen of methyl cratogolate diacetate. (Found: C, 73.68; H, 9.29. Calc. for C₃₃H₅₄O₆: C, 73.64; H, 9.54%).

Treatment of Ether-insoluble Fraction: (a). Acetone-soluble Part.—The ether-insoluble matter (18 g.) was digested with acetone and filtered from acetone-insoluble matter (10 g.). Evaporation of the solvent afforded a solid (6.8 g.) which on esterification with ethereal diazomethane, chromatography over alumina (150 g., deactivated with 4.5 ml of 10% acetic acid), and elution with benzene afforded a solid (2.6 g.). This on acetylation with acetic anhydride (25 ml) and pyridine (25 ml) in the usual manner and crystallisation from acetone furnished methyl oleanolate acetate, m.p. 214-18°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample. Elution with ether in the above chromatogram provided a crude solid (1.28 g.), m.p. 214-18°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and methanol afforded pure methyl cratogolate (0.32 g.), m.p. 225-27°, $[\alpha]_D^{+36}$ (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample. (Found: C, 76.14; H, 10.47; M.W. (Rast), 462. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₄: C, 76.50; H, 10.36%; M.W., 486).

(b). Acetone-insoluble Part.—The above acetone-insoluble solid (10 g.) was extracted with methanol and filtered. Evaporation of the solvent afforded a semicrystalline solid (7.8 g.) which was esterified with ethereal diazomethane. The ester mixture, thus obtained, was chromatographed over alumina (150 g., deactivated with 4.5 ml of 10% acetic acid). Elution with benzene afforded a solid (1.2 g.) which on acetylation with acetic anhydride (12 ml) and pyridine (12 ml) in the usual manner furnished methyl oleanolate acetate (0.31 g.), m.p. 218-20°, identical with an authentic specimen.

Elution with ether in the above chromatogram furnished a crystalline solid (2.3 g.) which on crystallisation from acetone afforded methyl cratogolate (0.4 g.), m.p. 216-18°,

identical with an authentic sample. (Found: C, 76.30; H, 10.47; M.W. (Rast), 465. Calc. for $C_{36}H_{50}O_4$: C, 76.50; H, 10.36%; M.W., 456).

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We have now been able to isolate methyl ursolate acetate, m.p. 238-42°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 65^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen, from the mother liquor of methyl oleanolate acetate, described above (added Dec. 1965).